

Software Quality Course Project

Introduction

You are working for the Quality Department of Lago Technologies, a tech company. Lago Technologies promotes internal entrepreneurship as one of its strategic policies. One of the outcomes from the implementation of this policy has been the invention of a promising IoT (Internet of Things) system called “Killer’IoT”, with several characteristics that makes of it a promising opportunity for a range of innovative products.

Lago Technologies top management has decided to create a spin-off for the business development of Killer’IoT. Business development will require, first, to identify an initial set of products, and then to develop these products in such a way that they can have a good place in very competitive market.

A consultancy company has advised that one of the key issues for the success of the spin-off is to define a suitable engineering process, supported by a quality management system, so that products can be developed in the shortest possible period of time, while products are technically sound and attractive to customers, aiming at high popularity. This engineering process will need to have an interface with the business processes that include marketing and sales. The inception of each product will be performed by a team with members from 1) the Engineering Department, 2) the Sales&Markets Department, accountable for all the business processes, and, 3) the StratG, the top management strategy group, with the support from 4) the Quality Department.

The top management has decided to launch an ideas competition in which several teams from each of the Departments will submit proposals. One proposal from each Department will be selected, and then, a joint team will co-create the engineering & business approach.

Your team must design the engineering management and quality management approaches. Processes will have to compliant with ISO 9000:2015 family.

It is relevant to know that the PDCA cycle is a pillar of Lago Technologies every-day work, and it is expected that it will be the case for the spin-off. Furthermore, for product development, the spinoff will follow the Lean start-up approach ¹, also aligned with the PDCA cycle.

Internally many discussions arose concerning the convenience of using an ISO 9000 scheme to underpin the spin-off quality system, because, supposedly, a lot of bureaucracy would be required and this is not welcome by the top management, following Hamel, G., & Zanini, M. (2018) ², and despite the opinions of some members of the Board. Consensus could be found

¹ <http://theleanstartup.com/principles>

² Hamel, G., & Zanini, M. (2018). The end of bureaucracy. *Harvard Business Review*, 96(6), 50-59.

thanks to some recent studies, such as Yu, K., Qian, C., & Chen, J. (2022)³. Furthermore, some guidelines on how ISO 9000 could be introduced for a start-up business case could be found in Anttila, J., & Jussila, K. (2021)⁴.

The management and quality management approaches have to include the different phases of the software systems/lifecycle targeting a successful product under a Total Quality approach. It will be important to show how and when value is added to the organization by making sure that customers will love the designed products.

The documentation to be provided will consist of two documents (deliverables) and a presentation, supported by a slide deck.

First Part: Quality Management System Specification

The Quality Management System Specification must include the following sections:

1. Introduction: Short description of commercial goals, clients, and services that the organization is offering to society.
2. Organizational Structure: Description of the organization's departments and managers, adapted to the spin-off.
3. Mission: purpose for existing as expressed by top management
4. Vision: aspiration of what an organization would like to become as expressed by top management
5. Strategy: guidelines to achieve a long-term or overall objective
6. Quality Policy.
7. Stakeholders: Employees, clients, and suppliers.
8. Processes list: Enumeration of strategic processes, key/operative processes and supporting processes that constitute the organizational Quality Plan related to Quality Management Processes involved into Customized Software Development and Services.
 - a. This list must content between 7 and 10 processes including a short description of each one of them.
 - b. To identify each one of the processes the following code must be used:
 - i. Strategic processes: (PR-ST-XX)
 - ii. Operational processes: (PR-OP-XX)
 - iii. Supporting processes: (PR-SP-XX)
9. ESG Criteria and SDGs.

³ Yu, K., Qian, C., & Chen, J. (2022). How does intelligent manufacturing reconcile the conflict between process standards and technological innovation?. *Journal of Engineering and Technology Management*, 65, 101698.

⁴ Anttila, J., & Jussila, K. (2021). ISO 9004-A stimulating quality management standard for the creative leaders of contemporary sustainable organizations. *Production engineering archives*, 27(2), 148-155.

Second Part: Process Specification

Processes to be defined are taken from the list of processes included in the Quality Management System Specification. You must include at least the same number of procedures as members of the group.

To describe the processes, you must use the model described in Activity 12.

Process documentation must include detailed description of documentation used as input and output data for the process, records, indicators and measures, forms, polls, data design, etc. You can use as guide different procedures available in Moodle.

It is mandatory that every procedure will include some important indicators in an explicit way, and if calculus is needed, how they are going to be calculated.

In the case that some forms had been defined to get or produce information for a process, you must include it/them into the process documentation as ANNEXES.

Reference material

ISO 9000 Introduction and Support Package: Guidance on the Concept and Use of the Process Approach for management systems (<https://short.upm.es/dsp7q>)

ISO/IEC/IEEE 90003:2018 Software engineering — Guidelines for the application of ISO 9001:2015 to computer software (UPM Library)

ISO/IEC/IEEE 12207:2017 Systems and software engineering — Software life cycle processes (UPM Library)